

Apsidal Motion in Eclipsing Binaries: AG Ari and V1665 Aql

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Abstract. This study presents the apsidal motion analysis of two eclipsing binaries with eccentric orbits, AG Ari ($P = 1.963$ days, $e = 0.089$) and V1665 Aql ($P = 3.881$ days, $e = 0.245$). Their O - C diagrams have been studied using all the minimum times found from the database/literature, and new values for the apsidal motion's parameters have been calculated for two target binaries. We found the apsidal motion's periods of the target systems of 147 ± 3 yr and 253 ± 7 yr for AG Ari and V1665 Aql, respectively.

Keywords: Eclipsing binaries stars, Apsidal motion, individual: AG Ari and V1665 Aql

INTRODUCTION

An important source for understanding stellar structure is an apsidal motion's study of the binary stars with eccentric orbits. There is a direct relationship between the apsidal motion of eclipsing binaries and the concentration of the internal density of the star. These studies provide observational testing of theoretical models of stellar evolution and their structure.

In this work, we presented an apsidal motion's analysis of the eclipsing V1665 Aql and AG Ari binaries. They are eclipsing binary systems with eccentric orbit. V1665 Aql is included in the catalog of elliptical orbital pairs given by Bulut and Demircan (2007).

APSIDAL MOTION ANALYSIS

Using the eclipse times of eclipsing binaries is a well-known method for analysing the apsidal motion of the target binary stars. We used for apsidal motion analyses of AG Ari and V1665 Aql the mathematical method recommended by Gimenez and Bastero (1995).

For the apsidal motion's analysis of the target binary systems were gathered all minima time from the literature. In addition, the TESS photometric data of V1665 Aql and AG Ari were used to generate the light curves of the systems.. We obtained primary and secondary times of minima.

AG ARI

AG Ari (HIC 11369, HD 15114, YZ 12 712, SKY# 3620, HIP 11369, AG+12 257, TD1 1423, ASAS J022627+1253.9, Gaia DR1 74428484704839552, Gaia DR2 74428489000457984, Gaia DR3 74428489000457984, TIC 408744603, 2MASS J02262695+1253558, PPM 118229, BD+12 332, TYC 638-290-1, SAO 92950, GSC 00638-00290, V* AG Ari; R.A. = $02^{\text{h}} 26^{\text{m}} 26^{\text{s}}.9617$, DEC = $+12^{\circ} 53' 55''.800$, $V_{\text{max}} = 8^{\text{m}}.18$, (Simbad) 8.16 – 8.42 (8.32), $P = 1.963115$ days) is a detached eclipsing binary systems. It was discovered in the NSV database by Kazarovets et al. (1999) as an eclipsing binary. Kreiner (2004) reported a relatively apsidal motion for AG Ari. The ground-based observations and radial velocities of the V1665 Aql and AG Ari binaries were provided by Ibanoglu et al. (2007). We have used the O-C database created by Paschke and Brát (2006) for the minimum times published in recent years. Kim et al. (2018) obtained the first apsidal motion elements for AG Ari. This analysis used a total of 23 (14 primary

and 9 secondary) minimum times for AG Ari. The light elements in Eq 1 were used to calculate the residuals from O-C:

$$HJD (MinI) = 2448501.2540 + 1^d.963115 \times E \quad (1)$$

The O-C values was calculated by Zasche (2009)'s program. The parameters of AG Ari derived from apsidal motion analysis are given in Table 1. The diagram of the period variation is also shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. The period variation of AG Ari. The filled circle and the open circle show the minima-I and the minima-II, respectively.

V1665 AQL

V1665 Aql (HD 175677, HIP 92943, SKY# 34894, YZ 7 8915, AG+07 2530, 2MASS J18560990+0756081, TD1 23524, Gaia DR2 4310055589131368576, BD+07 3898, NSV 24630, TIC 102969079, Gaia DR3 4310055589131368576, GSC 01039-01307, PPM 166831, TYC 1039-1307-1, Gaia DR1 4310055584830858112, HIC 92943, SAO 124069, V* V1665 Aql); R.A. = 18^h 56^m 09^s.90, DEC = +07° 56' 08".222, $V_{\max} = 8^m.11$ (Simbad) is a rather neglected eccentric orbiting binary system. V1665 Aql was discovered as an eclipsing binary star by Otero (2003). It was found in the ASAS, HIPPARCOS NSVS database. The ground-based observations and radial velocities of V1665 Aql were obtained by Ibanoglu et al. (2007). We used the minimum times published in the O-C database created by Paschke and Brát (2006) in the last several years. Kim et al. (2018) obtained the first apsidal motion elements for V1665 Aql.

A total of 9 (6 primary and 3 secondary) minimum times for V1665 Aql were used in this analysis. The residuals from O-C were obtained using the linear light elements in Eq 2:

$$HJD (MinI) = HJD 2452812.3600 + 3^d.88181 \times E \quad (2)$$

The O-C changing diagrams was obtained by Zasche (2009)'s program. The derived apsidal motion parameters for V1665 Aql are presented in Table 1. The O-C changing diagram of its period variation is also shown in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2. The period variation of V1665 Aql. The filled circle and the open circle show the minima-I and the minima-II, respectively.

TABLE 1. Apical motion parameters for V1665 Aql and AG Ari in this study.

Parametres	AG Ari	V1665 Aql
T_0 (HJD)	2448501.2296 ± 0.0168	2452810.7185 ± 0.1129
P_s [days]	1.963128 ± 0.000004	3.881757 ± 0.000229
P_a [days]	1.963200 ± 0.000004	3.881920 ± 0.000229
e	0.0892 ± 0.0141	0.2455 ± 0.0738
$\dot{\omega}$ [deg/cycle]	0.0131 ± 0.0002	0.0151 ± 0.0062
ω [deg]	73.7 ± 0.8	125.9 ± 4.8
U [yr]	147 ± 3	253 ± 7

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the apical motion parameters of two target binary systems with eccentric orbits were estimated. The apical motion periods of AG Ari and V1665 Aql were achieved to be 147 ± 3 years and 253 ± 7 years respectively. This shows that the apical motion in AG Ari is rapid. The orbital eccentricity of AG Ari and V1665 Aql were calculated as 0.0892 ± 0.0141 and 0.2455 ± 0.0738 , respectively.

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